

Cation and anion effect on the biodegradability and toxicity of imidazolium- and choline-based ionic liquids

I.F. Mena,^{*} E. Diaz, J. Palomar, J.J. Rodriguez, A.F. Mohedano

Chemical Engineering Department, University Autonoma de Madrid, C/ Francisco

Tomás y Valiente 7, 28049, Madrid, Spain. Phone: +34914978035, Fax: +34914973516

*Corresponding author: ismael.fernandez@uam.es

1 **Cation and anion effect on the biodegradability and toxicity of**
2 **imidazolium– and choline–based ionic liquids**

3

4 I.F. Mena,* E. Diaz, J. Palomar, J.J. Rodriguez, A.F. Mohedano

5

6 Chemical Engineering Department, University Autonoma de Madrid, C/ Francisco

7 Tomás y Valiente 7, 28049, Madrid, Spain. Phone: +34914978035, Fax: +34914973516

8 *Corresponding author: ismael.fernandez@uam.es

9

10 **Abstract**

11 This work studies the effect of the cation and anion on the biodegradability and
12 inhibition of imidazolium– and choline–based ionic liquids (ILs) using activated sludge.

13 Six commercial ILs, formed by combination of 1–Butyl–3–methylimidazolium
14 (Bmim⁺) and N,N,N–trimethylethanolammonium (Choline⁺) cations and chloride (Cl[–]),
15 acetate (Ac[–]) and bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (NTf₂[–]) anions were evaluated, all
16 representative counter–ions with markedly different toxicity and biodegradability.

17 Inherent and fast biodegradability tests were used to evaluate both the microorganism
18 inhibition and the IL biodegradability. In addition, the ecotoxicological response (EC₅₀)
19 of the ILs was studied using activated sludge and *Vibrio fischeri* (Microtox[®] test).

20 Bmim⁺ and NTf₂[–] can be considered as non–biodegradable, whereas aerobic
21 microorganisms easily degraded Choline⁺ and Ac[–]. The biodegradation pattern of each
22 cation/anion is nearly unaffected by counter–ion nature. Moreover, concentrations of
23 CholineNTf₂ higher than 50 mg/L caused a partial inhibition on microbial activity, in
24 good concordance with its low EC₅₀ (54 mg/L) measured by respiration inhibition test,
25 which alerts on the negative environmental impact of NTf₂–containing ILs on the
26 performance of sewage treatment plants.

27

28 Keywords: Activated sludge; biodegradability; choline; ecotoxicity; imidazolium.

29

30 **1. Introduction**

31 Ionic liquids are salts with a melting point lower than 100 °C at 1 atm formed through
32 the combination of an organic cation and organic or inorganic anion with interesting
33 properties such as low vapor pressure and physical and chemical stability. They have
34 been designed to be robust at several reaction conditions and, consequently, to become
35 essential chemicals as reaction solvents, battery electrolytes, lubricants, surfactants,
36 catalysts, dielectric fluids as transformers and capacitors (Olivier–Bourbigou et al.,
37 2010; Plechkova and Seddon, 2008). However, several studies have questioned the
38 impact of these compounds on the environment suggesting that not all of them can be
39 considered as green chemicals (Jordan and Gathergood, 2015; Richardson and Ternes,
40 2014). Recent works have made evident how the release of ILs to the aquatic
41 environment could cause an environmental concern, due to some of them are considered
42 as toxic and non–biodegradable (Amde et al., 2015; Chatel et al., 2017; Diaz et al.,
43 2016; Frade and Afonso, 2010; Thuy Pham et al., 2010). In this context, these aspects
44 must be included in the studies focused on the whole life cycle of ILs in order to
45 establish a real eco–design strategy of the IL.

46 Some biodegradability assays can be useful to determine ILs biodegradability in the
47 environment and minimize negative impacts due to its persistence and/or accumulation
48 (Polo et al., 2011; Sanchis et al., 2014). Ecotoxicological determinations, which are
49 dependent on the studied model and environment conditions, can be used at a first
50 assessment of the potential effect of ILs on a specific group of aquatic organisms (Costa
51 et al., 2015b; Khan et al., 2016). In both cases, it is essential to select those assays
52 whose results provide realistic effects of the exposure risk to ILs, and let i) know more

53 about the impact of these compounds on sewage wastewater treatment; and ii) select an
54 efficient degradation process to remove them from water (Diaz et al., 2016; Peric et al.,
55 2013; Richardson and Kimura, 2016).

56 The choice of an adequate test must consider the end–point discharge of wastewater
57 and, consequently, try to predict the behavior of ILs in sewage treatment plants.
58 Different biodegradation methods have been adopted by OECD and ISO (Diaz et al.,
59 2016; Jordan and Gathergood, 2015; Pagga, 1997) to provide biodegradation data as the
60 OECD 301B (biodegradation test, CO₂ evolution) (Stolte et al., 2012), the OECD 301D
61 (biodegradation closed bottle test) (Stolte et al., 2008), the OECD 301F (biodegradation
62 test, O₂ consumption) (Neumann et al., 2014b) and the OECD 310 (ready
63 biodegradability, CO₂ in sealed vessels) (Atefi et al., 2009; Ford et al., 2010; Pretti et
64 al., 2011). Specifically, Zahn–Wellens test (OECD 302B) evaluates the inherent
65 biodegradability of water pollutants along 28 days, being the main disadvantage the
66 great amount of time required to complete the assay. In this sense, a simple and fast
67 respirometric test, based on the typical operation conditions of an activated sludge
68 process, which provides data from the activity of the microorganisms and pollutant
69 removal, has been proposed to obtain biodegradability data in a relatively short–time
70 (100 h) (Polo et al., 2011).

71 Previous results focused on the biodegradability of ILs have established some rules of
72 thumb. According to structural design, both the head group and the substituted side
73 chain have influence on the IL degradability. The following sequence of
74 biodegradability could be established regarding head group as long as the same side
75 chain is substituted: pyrrolidinium $\approx$ pyridinium > piperidinium $\approx$ morpholinium >>
76 imidazolium (Neumann et al., 2014a). In general, regardless IL family, the
77 biodegradability increases as the length of alkyl chain of cation or by the introduction in

78 these chains of functional groups such as hydroxyl, carboxylic, alcohol or ether
79 (Egorova and Ananikov, 2014; Jordan and Gathergood, 2015). On the other hand, the
80 use of natural building blocks as choline or nicotinic acid as IL cations has a positive
81 influence on the biodegradability. In relation to the anion, organic anions (carboxylic
82 acids, amino acids, carbohydrates) can be considered as biodegradable. In the case of
83 inorganic anions, their biodegradation cannot take into account, but while halide anions
84 (chloride or bromide) do not interfere on the potential biodegradability of the IL, the
85 degradation of ILs with perfluorinated anions (PF_6^- , BF_4^-) can lead to more toxic
86 compounds (Freire et al., 2010; Gathergood et al., 2006; Jordan and Gathergood, 2015).

87 With regard to the ecotoxicity, standardized tests can provide different behavior
88 depending on the microorganism employed in the assays (Rizzo, 2011), and again,
89 underestimate or overestimate the behavior of the aquatic system in the presence of a
90 certain pollutant. The standardized toxicity tests traditionally used are: ISO 11348, to
91 determine the inhibitory effect of water samples (*Vibrio fischeri*) (Costa et al., 2015a;
92 Diaz et al., 2018; Docherty and Kulpa, Jr., 2005; Garcia et al., 2005; Montalbán et al.,
93 2018; Oulego et al., 2018; Ventura et al., 2014; Viboud et al., 2012); ISO 8692, to
94 determine the growth inhibition of unicellular green algae by substances and mixtures
95 contained in water (*Selenastrum capricornutum*) (Cho et al., 2008; Stolte et al., 2012);
96 USEPA–ISO 6341, to determine the inhibition of the mobility of *Daphnia magna*
97 *Straus* (acute toxicity test) (Costa et al., 2015b; Samori et al., 2010; Stolte et al., 2012;
98 Vieira et al., 2019); or OECD 201, to determine the effect of a substance on the growth
99 of freshwater microalgae and/or cyanobacteria (*Scenedesmus rubescens*) (Tsarpali and
100 Dailianis, 2015). Despite of Microtox® test is not a standard toxicity test defined in the
101 European Union legislation, it is widely accepted to establish a first–approach of a
102 toxicity of a xenobiotic compound due to be fast, simple and cost–efficient (Sintra et al.,

103 2017). However, *Vibrio fischeri* is not representative of the microorganisms that
104 constitute a sewage sludge. In this sense and following the idea to obtain useful
105 ecotoxicity data to establish a reliable assessment of potential toxicity of a xenobiotic in
106 a sewage treatment plant, a respiration inhibition test using activated sludge (OECD 209
107 – Activated Sludge, Respiration Inhibition Test (Carbon and Ammonium Oxidation)) is
108 recommendable (Polo et al., 2011; Rizzo, 2011). Although it is well known that toxicity
109 of ILs depends on the nature of a biological system, there are some factors that seem to
110 modulate the ILs toxicity: i) length of an alkyl chain in the cation; ii) degree and nature
111 of functionalization in the side chain of the cation; iii) nature of the anion; iv) nature of
112 the cation; and v) mutual influence of anion and cation (Egorova and Ananikov, 2014).
113 In general, an increase of the alkyl chain length causes a drastic increase of the toxicity,
114 which seems to be related to the high lipophilic character, and the introduction of
115 oxygenated groups provokes a decrease on IL toxicity (Costello et al., 2009; Cvjetko
116 Bubalo et al., 2014; Diaz et al., 2016; Ranke et al., 2007; Stolte et al., 2007). Despite of
117 the fact that the anion nature contributes less than the cation to the overall IL toxicity,
118 the toxicity of anions as NTf_2^- and C_8SO_4^- must not be underestimated, being this
119 contribution more evident in the case of IL with short cation alkyl chain (Diaz et al.,
120 2018; Petkovic et al., 2011).

121 Moreover, in order to study the called PBT assessment (persistence, bioaccumulation,
122 toxicity), some authors have focused their research in the bioconcentration potential of
123 the ILs (Bingham and Ballone, 2012; Dołzonek et al., 2017; Jing et al., 2016; Yoo et al.,
124 2014). In general, imidazolium ILs containing cations with long alkyl side chain (> 8 C
125 atoms) can intercalate into the lipid membrane bilayer (Dołzonek et al., 2017; Jing et al.,
126 2016). In terms of anions, ILs constituted by NTf_2^- present higher bilayer disruption
127 than those with contain chloride anion (Jing et al., 2016).

128 ILs show in general high thermal and chemical stability together with low
129 biodegradability, which do not favor their removal from aqueous effluents. Adsorption
130 of ILs on different materials, such as active carbon, alumina or silica, provides a way to
131 recover them (Lemus et al., 2012; Neves et al., 2014). Moreover, ILs have been
132 effectively degraded by means of AOPS such as Fenton oxidation (Dominguez et al.,
133 2014; Munoz et al., 2015; Gomez–Herrero et al., 2018), catalytic wet peroxide
134 oxidation (Mena et al., 2019b; Munoz et al., 2016), photodegradation (Bedia et al.,
135 2019; Leonardo da Silva et al., 2019; Stepnowski et al., 2005), electroxidation (Mena et
136 al., 2019a; Pieczyńska et al., 2015) or electro–Fenton processes (Bocos et al., 2017;
137 Poza–Nogueiras et al., 2018).

138 In this work, we study the toxicity and biodegradability of several imidazolium– and
139 choline–based ILs in order to analyze their potential behavior in a sewage treatment
140 plant, taking into account the effect of anion and cation. Thus, inherent (Zahn–Wellens)
141 and fast biodegradability tests have been performed. Respiration inhibition test, using
142 activated sludge, has been employed to evaluate ILs toxicity. With respect to ILs,
143 imidazolium family presents a huge potential for industrial applications (Chatel et al.,
144 2017). They have been used as surfactants (Bhadani et al., 2016; Nandwani et al.,
145 2017), in CO₂ absorption (Karadas et al., 2013) and as solvents (Cull et al., 2000) and
146 homogeneous catalysts in organic reactions (Pârvulescu and Hardacre, 2007). Bmim⁺,
147 used as representative species of the imidazolium family, has been studied in electro
148 synthesis of organic compounds (Kathiresan and Velayutham, 2015), CO₂ absorption
149 (Moya et al., 2016) and as catalysts in organic reactions, such as hydrogenation or
150 alkylation (Zhao et al., 2002). On the other hand, choline–based ILs refers to a
151 quaternary ammonium salts with a counter anion, with application in organic synthesis
152 and polymerization reactions (Liu et al., 2015; Plechkova and Seddon, 2008; Zhang et

153 al., 2012), NH₃ and CO₂ absorption (Palomar et al., 2011; Pandey et al., 2013),
154 fractionation of lignocellulosic biomass for biofuel production (An et al., 2015),
155 cellulose decrystallization (Zhang et al., 2012) and dyes degradation (Sekar et al.,
156 2012). In the last years, the latter have shown a huge potential to replace traditional
157 organic solvents, which have apparently shown a lower adverse environmental impact
158 than imidazolium-based ILs (Gadilohar and Shankarling, 2017; Petkovic et al., 2011).
159 The selected anions were chloride (Cl⁻) and acetate (Ac⁻), representative hydrophilic
160 inorganic and organic anions, respectively, and also bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide
161 (NTf₂⁻) as hydrophobic anion.

162 **2. Materials and methods**

163 2.1. Ionic liquids

164 Table 1 collects the ionic liquids from imidazolium (1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium,
165 Bmim⁺) and choline (N,N,N-trimethylethanolammonium, Choline⁺) families with
166 chloride (Cl⁻), acetate (Ac⁻) and bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (NTf₂⁻) as anions,
167 used in this study, together with their nomenclature. The ILs were supplied by Sigma-
168 Aldrich and Iolitec with a purity higher than 95 %.

169 **Table 1.** Chemical structure and nomenclature of imidazolium- and choline-based ILs.

Anion	Cation
 Bmim ⁺	
 Ac ⁻	
 Choline ⁺	

170

171 2.2. Inoculum and culture medium

172 Unacclimated activated sludge, obtained from a domestic sewage treatment plant, has
173 been used as inoculum in the biodegradability assays (inherent biodegradability and fast
174 biodegradability tests) and in the respiration inhibition tests (OECD 209, ISO 8192).
175 The sludge was maintained in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR) operated at room

176 temperature using an organic loading rate (sodium acetate and glucose) of 0.4 mg
177 COD/mg VSS·day. Ammonium sulphate and phosphoric acid were used as nitrogen and
178 phosphorous sources, respectively. A COD:N:P of 100:5:1 (w/w) was fixed and mineral
179 salts (FeCl₃, CaCl₂, KCl and MgCl₂) were also added as micronutrients supply in a
180 COD:micronutrients (Fe, Ca, K and Mg) ratio of 100:0.05 (w/w).

181 2.3. Inherent biodegradability test

182 The Zahn–Wellens test (OECD 302 B 1992) was carried by triplicate in amber glass
183 reactors (2.5 L) with 10 mg/L of IL in aqueous solution. The IL carbon content to
184 inoculum (dry–weight) ratio was 1:4 and mineral medium (phosphate buffer with CaCl₂
185 (27.5 mg/L), MgSO₄·7H₂O (22.5 mg/L) and FeCl₃·6H₂O (0.25 mg/L)) was also added.
186 The mixture was agitated and aerated at room temperature for 28 days. A control test
187 using ethylene glycol was carried out in order to ensure the activity of the sludge.
188 Samples were taken periodically to quantify the TOC and IL concentration. The results
189 reported are the average values from duplicate runs, the standard errors being always
190 lower than 10%.

191 2.4. Fast biodegradability test

192 Fast biodegradability tests were carried out in close reactors with a mixture of
193 unacclimated activated sludge (350 mg/L), IL (10 and 50 mg/L) and mineral medium as
194 previously described (Polo et al., 2011). The evolution of IL concentration, TOC and
195 specific oxygen uptake rate (SOUR) profile was registered. Experiments were carried
196 out in duplicate. The standard errors of the measurements were always lower than 10%.

197 2.5. Respirometric inhibition assay

198 Respiration inhibition tests for activated sludge were carried out according to the
199 method proposed by Polo et al. (2011). The procedure consisted in short–term
200 respirometric measurements carried out in a Liquid–Static–Static (LSS) respirometer

201 (Chica et al., 2007), using unacclimated sludge (350 mgVSS/L) in the presence of an
202 easily biodegradable substrate (sodium acetate) alone or together with different
203 concentrations of the ILs. The biomass activity was measured in terms of SOUR.
204 Inhibition was also estimated in terms of EC₅₀ defined as the effective concentration of
205 a sample that causes 50% reduction of SOUR. Experiments were performed in
206 triplicate, being the standard deviation below 10 %.

207 2.6. Ecotoxicity test

208 Ecotoxicity measurements were performed according to standard Microtox test
209 procedure (ISO 11348, 2007), based on the decreasing of light emission by the marine
210 bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* (*Photobacterium phosphoreum*) after 15 min in presence of IL
211 at pH within 6–8, using a Microtox M500 Analyzer (Azur Environmental). The results
212 were expressed in terms of EC₅₀, defined as the effective concentration of IL that causes
213 a 50 % inhibitory effect. The results reported were the average values from triplicate
214 measurements. The standard errors of the measurements were always lower than 10%.

215 2.7. Analytical methods

216 Bmim⁺ was analyzed by means of HPLC (Varian Pro–Start 240) with a visible UV
217 detector (Prostar 325 UV–Vis) at 218 nm. A Synergy 4 mm Polar–RP 80 A
218 (Phenomenex) column (15 cm length, 4.6 mm diameter) was used as stationary phase
219 and a mixture of acetonitrile and water (5:95, v/v) at 0.75 mL/min as mobile phase.

220 Choline⁺ identification was carried out by means of ionic chromatography (Metrohm
221 790 Persona IC) fitted with a Metrosep C4–250/4.0 column as stationary phase. The
222 mobile phase (0.9 mL/min) was a mixture of 0.7 mM of 2,6–pyridinedicarboxylic acid
223 and 1.7 mM of HNO₃. Ion chromatography with chemical suppression (DIONEX ICS–
224 900) was employed to detect the anionic species (chloride and acetate) using a Dionex
225 IonPac AS22 4 x 250 mm column at 1 mL/min of 1.4 mM NaHCO₃/4.5 mM Na₂CO₃ as

226 mobile phase. The NTf_2^- anion was identified by liquid chromatography coupled with
227 mass spectrometry (LC/MS SQ Agilent) fitted with an ACE Excel 3 C18–Amide, 250 x
228 2.1 mm column at 40 °C as stationary phase. A formic acid (0.1 % v/v) and acetonitrile
229 (10:90 % v/v) at 0.2 mL/min was used as mobile phase. Total organic carbon (TOC)
230 was measured using a TOC apparatus from Shimadzu (Shimadzu TOC–VCSH). Before
231 analysis, samples were filtered through 0.45 μm syringe filters (OlimPeak PTFE, 25
232 mm, Teknokroma).

233 3. Results and discussion

234 Figure 1 show the biodegradability of Bmim–based ILs by Zahn–Wellens test. In
235 preliminary tests, neither ILs volatilization nor adsorption occurred during the testing
236 period. In the case of Bmim–based ILs, no biodegradation was observed for BmimCl
237 and BmimNTf₂. This fact has also observed by previous studies by means of the Closed
238 Bottle Test (OECD 301D) (Garcia et al., 2005) and the biological oxygen demand test
239 (BOD_5) (Quijano et al., 2011; Romero et al., 2008). Regarding the Bmim⁺ removal,
240 Quijano et al. (2011) did not find any evidence of degradation of Bmim⁺ (BmimNTf₂,
241 10 mg/L) in a long–term biodegradability test for 30 days using activated sludge.
242 However, a partial Bmim⁺ biodegradation (BmimCl, 130 mg/L), without transformation
243 of the imidazolium core, can be reached in less than 40 days using an enriched activated
244 sludge (Alisawi et al., 2017; Docherty et al., 2015). In this study, only a partial
245 biodegradation happened for BmimAc IL (Figure 1b), which was attributed to the
246 complete mineralization of acetate anion in the first 3h. Along the experimental time,
247 biomass did not adapt to degrade Bmim⁺ or NTf₂⁻. On the other hand, organic acid
248 anions, as acetate, appear to be the best selection for promoting biodegradability of ILs
249 (Jordan and Gathergood, 2015; Quijano et al., 2011).

250 In the case of choline-based ILs (Figure 2), choline cation can be considered
251 biodegradable, showing complete removal in less than 6 days. In a recent work we
252 identified some species, like ethanol, and methyl-, dimethyl- and trimethylamine in the
253 degradation pathway of Choline⁺ in a sequencing batch reactor using conventional
254 activated sludge (Mena et al., 2019c). However, only acetate anion (CholineAc) was
255 totally degraded in few hours. As can be seen in Figures 1 and 2, the separately
256 observed biodegradability of each cation or anion does not seem be strongly affected by
257 the nature of the counter-ion. It suggests that IL biodegradation occurs through
258 dissociated ionic species in water, rather than ion-pair or associated species. TOC
259 significantly decreased during the first hours, and after that time, a lower TOC removal
260 rate was observed. TOC conversion achieved 85 and 87 % for CholineCl and
261 CholineAc, respectively, and consequently, both compounds can be considered
262 biodegradables. The biodegradability of CholineCl has been previously observed
263 according to the ready biodegradability test 301D OECD, reaching more than 90 %
264 removal within 14 days (Radošević et al., 2015), and by means of the biological oxygen
265 demand test (BOD₅) (Gadilohar et al. 2014). For CholineNTf₂, Radošević et al. (2015)
266 evidenced Choline⁺ degradation together with a TOC removal of ~70 % corresponding
267 to the cation mineralization.

269

270 **Figure 1.** Time course of (a) BmimCl, (b) BmimAc, (c) BmimNTf₂ and TOC removal along Zahn–Wellens test.

271

272 **Figure 2.** Time course of CholineCl (a), CholineAc (b), and CholineNTf₂ (c) and TOC removal along Zahn–Wellens test.

273 ILs biodegradability was further measured by the fast biodegradability respirometric test
274 (Polo et al., 2011). Figure 3 shows the time course of SOUR and the concentration of
275 each cation and anion for Bmim-based ILs using an initial concentration of 10 and 50
276 mg/L. Time-evolution ILs concentration is maintained practically unalterable for
277 BmimCl and BmimNTf₂, regardless of the IL initial concentration. The respirometric
278 profiles did not suffer any significant changes for the lowest IL concentration (10
279 mg/L), whereas an initial decay of endogenous respiration was observed for the highest
280 one (50 mg/L), which could be attributed to the partial inhibition of the microbial
281 activity, followed by a slight increase of the sludge respiration after an adaptation time.
282 The unacclimated sludge was able to degrade acetate concentrations of 3 and 15 mg/L
283 in the first 8 h for BmimAc. SOUR values were proportional to the initial acetate
284 concentration, and after the complete decay of this substrate, the microbial activity
285 remained unalterable. The results of the fast biodegradability test are comparable to the
286 obtained by the Zahn–Wellens test, although the former also indicates that a
287 concentration of BmimNTf₂ superior to 50 mg/L can cause detrimental effects on the
288 biomass, which seems to be related to the highest toxicity attributed to NTf₂⁻ (Diaz et
289 al., 2018; Santos et al., 2014).

290

291 **Figure 3.** Time course of IL concentration and SOUR profiles along the respirometric assays for an initial concentration of 10 mg/L (BmimCl
 292 (a), BmimAc (b), and BmimNTf₂ (c)) and 50 mg/L (BmimCl (d), BmimAc (e), and BmimNTf₂ (f)).

293 The respirometric profiles obtained using 10 mg/L choline ILs (Figure 4) showed an
294 increase of sludge respiration, after an acclimation time, which is associated with
295 Choline⁺ degradation. In the case of CholineCl, the presence of Cl⁻ did not interfere to
296 Choline⁺ removal, whereas in presence of organic anions as Ac⁻ and NTf₂⁻, the cation
297 transformation happened at a lower rate. It could be related, on the one hand, to the fast
298 assimilation of acetate as carbon source for the microorganisms, which took place in the
299 first 8 h of the experiment, and on the other hand, to the presence of a non-
300 biodegradable compound in the reaction medium as NTf₂⁻. An increase of the choline-
301 based ILs concentration (50 mg/L) did not cause any important effect on the microbial
302 activity in the case of CholineCl and CholineAc. In both cases, the respirometric
303 profiles were similar to that obtained with a lower concentration, except that the
304 maximum value of the SOUR was higher for the highest IL concentration. It may be
305 related to the hydrophilic nature of Cl⁻ and Ac⁻ anions, which promotes their solvation
306 by water molecular and the dominant presence of dissociated ionic species in the
307 solution (Li et al., 2007; Palomar et al., 2007; Stassen et al., 2015). In the case of
308 CholineNTf₂, a fall of the endogenous respiration took placed along the first hours of
309 the assay and neither degradation of Choline⁺ nor NTf₂⁻ were observed. This suggests
310 that CholineNTf₂, at the highest concentration used (50 mg/L), caused a negative effect
311 on the microbial diversity of sewage sludge, probably due to the hydrophobic nature of
312 this anion, which promotes the presence of aggregated cation-anion species as
313 increasing IL concentration (Li et al., 2007; Stassen et al., 2015). Ion-pair structures are
314 less polar and more lipophilic than dissociated ions (González et al., 2018), increasing
315 the toxic effects of the IL compound and preventing its biodegradation (Torrecilla et al.,
316 2010).

317

318 **Figure 4.** Time course of IL concentration and SOUR profiles along the respirometric assays for an initial concentration of 10 mg/L (CholineCl
 319 (a), CholineAc (b), and CholineNTf₂ (c)) and 50 mg/L (CholineCl (d), CholineAc (e), and CholineNTf₂ (f)).

320 In order to gain information on the toxicity of Bmim⁻ and choline⁻ based ILs, a series of
321 respirometric tests were carried out for each IL over a wide range of concentrations (10
322 – 500 mg/L), with the aim of establishing the inhibition of the activated sludge in terms
323 of EC₅₀ values. In spite of the fact that the required time to carry out the experiments is
324 less than 30 min, it was not possible to obtain values of EC₅₀ for compounds constituted
325 by an easily biodegradable substrate as acetate, since in these cases, an increase in the
326 BmimAc or CholineAc concentration did not cause a proportional decrease on the
327 respiration rate of the microorganisms. This was also observed in the case of the
328 experiments performed adding different concentrations of CholineCl, because of the
329 high biodegradability of Choline⁺, and Cl⁻ did not show an intrinsic toxicity effect.

330 However, as can be seen in the Figure 5, the high toxicity associated with the anion
331 NTf₂⁻ allowed establishing an EC₅₀ value of 140 μM using activated sludge for
332 CholineNTf₂, which is equivalent to 54 mg/L. Additionally, the NTf₂⁻ can be considered
333 as a potential toxic species due to the possible formation of hydrofluoric acid from the
334 hydrolysis of the fluorine component (Costa et al., 2015). Furthermore, the high toxicity
335 associated to NTf₂⁻ has been related to its high hydrophobicity (Costa et al., 2015b;
336 Ranke et al., 2007) and the ability of the anion to permeate on the cell membrane,
337 essentially non-polar (Dołzonek et al., 2017). This negative effect of NTf₂⁻ respect Cl⁻
338 and Ac⁻ is accentuated because the cations studied are less likely to interact with
339 membranes (Diaz et al., 2018), making evident the anion role on the ILs ecotoxicity.

340 This value could explain the behavior exhibited by the microbial population of the
341 activated sludge in the biodegradability assay (Figure 4f), which was exposed to an
342 inhibitory concentration of CholineNTf₂. Moreover, EC₅₀ values of 2691 μM for
343 BmimCl and 257 μM for BmimNTf₂, which are equivalent to 470 and 108 mg/L,
344 respectively, could be also determined, due to both ILs did not present biodegradability.

345 For comparison purposes, the EC_{50} values determined by Microtox® test are also
346 showed in Figure 5. Among the ILs studied, those constituted by Cl^- and Ac^- presented
347 the highest EC_{50} values, evidencing their environmentally friendly behavior (Couling et
348 al., 2006), being slightly lower the EC_{50} values associated to Bmim ILs than to choline
349 ILs. This fact agrees with the ILs with aromatic rings present more toxicity than those
350 with non-aromatic groups (Costa et al., 2015b). On the other hand, the presence of the
351 anion NTf_2^- in the IL structure caused a considerable ecotoxicity increase. In general,
352 the influence of the anion on the toxicity of IL has been considered of minor
353 importance, but the results of this test makes evident that some anions, specifically
354 those that contain fluorine atoms in their structure, can affect drastically to the IL
355 toxicity (Costa et al., 2015b; Diaz et al., 2018; Matzke et al., 2007; Montalbán et al.,
356 2016). The comparison of the results obtained for both tests lets conclude that the
357 Microtox test can be used to establish a toxicity trend about the behavior of ILs on the
358 activated sludge of a wastewater treatment plant. However, it is important to take into
359 account that this test may not anticipate the toxicity of an IL on the activated sludge of
360 wastewater plants, being more evident in the cases of the ILs constituted by NTf_2^- .

361

362 **Figure 5.** EC_{50} values (μM) for imidazolium and choline based ILs towards activated
363 sludge and *Vibrio fischeri*.

364 **4. Conclusions**

365 The detailed analysis of the evolution of the ILs concentration along biodegradability
366 studies revealed that BmimNTf₂ could not be degraded by an activated sludge, even at
367 low concentrations (10 mg/L), whereas CholineAc concentrations up to 50 mg/L can be
368 completely removed. Moreover, the microorganisms can assimilate Choline⁺ and
369 acetate as constituents of other ILs, depending on the structure and the concentration of
370 the counter-ion. A partial inhibition of the microbial activity was observed in the fast
371 biodegradability test performed with 50 mg/L of CholineNTf₂.

372 EC₅₀ values from Microtox Test for BmimCl and CholineCl lead the conclusion that
373 toxic effects of these ILs are directly related to both ILs constituents. Choline⁺ was
374 slightly less toxic than Bmim⁺ and that the presence of NTf₂⁻ increased considerably the
375 toxicity of ILs. According to the results from inhibition tests, ILs formed by a natural
376 building block as Choline⁺ can lead to nontoxic ILs for activated sludge microbiota, as
377 well as occurred with Ac⁻ in BmimAc and CholineAc. However, the presence of an
378 anion with intrinsic toxicity as NTf₂⁻ must not be underestimated, being this negative
379 contribution more evident in Choline⁺ ILs than in Bmim⁺ ones. Consequently, the
380 negative environmental impact of NTf₂-containing ILs should take into account for
381 their use in chemical processes, which can generate aqueous wastes.

382 **Acknowledgements**

383 The authors greatly appreciate financial support from the Spanish MINECO
384 (CTM2016-76564-R), Comunidad de Madrid (BIOTRES-CM, S2018/EMT-4344),
385 and UAM-Santander (CEAL-AL/2015-08). I.F. Mena wishes to thank the MINECO
386 and the ESF for a research grant (BES-2014-069986). The valuable contribution of J.
387 Lemus is also acknowledged.

388 **References**

- 389 Alisawi, W.A., Rahbarirad, S., Walker, K.A., Venter, A.R., Docherty, K.M.,
390 Szymczyna, B.R., 2017. Identification of metabolites produced during the complete
391 biodegradation of 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride by an enriched activated
392 sludge microbial community. *Chemosphere* 167, 53–61.
- 393 Amde, M., Liu, J., Pang, L., 2015. Environmental application, fate, effects and concerns
394 of ionic liquids: A review. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 49, 12611–12627.
395 doi:10.1021/acs.est.5b03123.
- 396 An, Y.X., Zong, M.H., Wu, H., Li, N., 2015. Pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass
397 with renewable cholinium ionic liquids: Biomass fractionation, enzymatic
398 digestion and ionic liquid reuse. *Bioresour. Technol.* 192, 165–171.
399 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2015.05.064.
- 400 Atefi, F., Garcia, M.T., Singer, R.D., Scammells, P.J., 2009. Phosphonium ionic liquids:
401 design, synthesis and evaluation of biodegradability. *Green Chem.* 11, 1595–
402 1604. doi:10.1039/b913057h.
- 403 Bedia, J., Rodriguez, J.J., Moreno, D., Palomar, J., Belver, C., 2019. Photostability and
404 photocatalytic degradation of ionic liquids in water under solar light. *RSC Adv.* 9,
405 2026–2033. doi:10.1039/c8ra07867j.
- 406 Bhadani, A., Misono, T., Singh, S., Sakai, K., Sakai, H., Abe, M., 2016. Structural
407 diversity, physicochemical properties and application of imidazolium surfactants:
408 Recent advances. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* 231, 36–58.
409 doi:10.1016/j.cis.2016.03.005.
- 410 Bingham, R.J., Ballone, P., 2012. Computational study of room-temperature ionic
411 liquids interacting with a POPC phospholipid bilayer. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 116,
412 11205–11216. doi:10.1021/jp306126q.
- 413 Bocos, E., González-Romero, E., Pazos, M., Sanromán, M.A., 2017. Application of
414 electro-Fenton treatment for the elimination of 1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium
415 triflate from polluted water. *Chem. Eng. J.* 318, 19–28.
416 doi:10.1016/j.cej.2016.04.058.

- 417 Chatel, G., Naffrechoux, E., Draye, M., 2017. Avoid the PCB mistakes: A more
418 sustainable future for ionic liquids. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 324, 773–780.
419 doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2016.11.060.
- 420 Chica, A.F., Martin, A., Vazquez, F.J., Carmona, F.J., Mohedo, J. Respirometer to
421 analyze measure dissolved oxygen and oxygen demand of microbes in leachate
422 from municipal waste. ES 2283171, 2007.
- 423 Cho, C.-W., Jeon, Y.-C., Pham, T.P.T., Vijayaraghavan, K., Yun, Y.-S., 2008. The
424 ecotoxicity of ionic liquids and traditional organic solvents on microalga
425 *Selenastrum capricornutum*. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 71, 166–171.
426 doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2007.07.001.
- 427 Costa, S.P.F., Pinto, P.C.A.G., Lapa, R.A.S., Saraiva, M.L.M.F.S., 2015a. Toxicity
428 assessment of ionic liquids with *Vibrio fischeri*: An alternative fully automated
429 methodology. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 284, 136–142.
430 doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2014.10.049.
- 431 Costa, S.P.F., Pinto, P.C.A.G., Saraiva, M.L.M.F.S., Rocha, F.R.P., Santos, J.R.P.,
432 Monteiro, R.T.R., 2015b. The aquatic impact of ionic liquids on freshwater
433 organisms. *Chemosphere* 139, 288–294. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.05.100.
- 434 Costello, D.M., Brown, L.M., Lamberti, G.A., 2009. Acute toxic effects of ionic liquids
435 on zebra mussel (*Dreissena polymorpha*) survival and feeding. *Green Chem.* 11,
436 548–553. doi:10.1039/b822347e.
- 437 Couling, D.J., Bernot, R.J., Docherty, K.M., Dixon, J.K., Maginn, E.J., 2006. Assessing
438 the factors responsible for ionic liquid toxicity to aquatic organisms via
439 quantitative structure–property relationship modeling. *Green Chem.* 8, 82–90.
440 doi:10.1039/B511333D.
- 441 Cull, S.G., Holbrey, J.D., Vargas–Mora, V., Seddon, K.R., Lye, G.J., 2000. Room-
442 temperature ionic liquids as replacements for organic solvents in multiphase
443 bioprocess operations. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 69, 227–233. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1097-
444 0290(20000720)69:2%3C227::AID-BIT12%3E3.0.CO;2-0.
- 445 Cvjetko Bubalo, M., Radošević, K., Radojčić Redovniković, I., Halambek, J., Gaurina
446 Srček, V., 2014. A brief overview of the potential environmental hazards of ionic

447 liquids. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 99, 1–12. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2013.10.019.

448 Diaz, E., Monsalvo, V., Palomar, J., Mohedano, A.F., 2016. Ionic liquids: Bacterial
449 degradation in wastewater treatment plants, *Encycl. Inorg. Bioinorg. Chem.*, John
450 Wiley & Sons, Ltd. doi:10.1002/9781119951438.eibc2393.

451 Diaz, E., Monsalvo, V.M., Lopez, J., Mena, I.F., Palomar, J., Rodriguez, J.J.,
452 Mohedano, A.F., 2018. Assessment the ecotoxicity and inhibition of imidazolium
453 ionic liquids by respiration inhibition assays. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 162, 29–
454 34. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2018.06.057.

455 Docherty, K.M., Kulpa Jr., C.F., 2005. Toxicity and antimicrobial activity of
456 imidazolium and pyridinium ionic liquids. *Green Chem.* 7, 185–189.
457 doi:10.1039/b419172b.

458 Docherty, K.M., Aiello, S.W., Buehler, B.K., Jones, S.E., Szymczyna, B.R., Walker,
459 K.A.C.F., 2015. Ionic liquid biodegradability depends on specific wastewater
460 microbial consortia. *Chemosphere* 136, 160–166.
461 doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.05.016.

462 Dołzonek, J., Cho, C.-W., Stepnowski, P., Markiewicz, M., Thöming, J., Stolte, S.,
463 2017. Membrane partitioning of ionic liquids cations, anions, and ion pairs –
464 Estimating the bioconcentration potential of organic ions. *Environ. Pollut.* 228,
465 378–389. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2017.04.079.

466 Dominguez, C.M., Munoz, M., Quintanilla, A., de Pedro, Z.M., Ventura, S.P.M.,
467 Coutinho, J.A.P., Casas, J.A., Rodriguez, J.J., 2014. Degradation of imidazolium-
468 based ionic liquids in aqueous solution by Fenton oxidation. *J. Chem. Technol.*
469 *Biotechnol.* 89, 1197–1202. doi:10.1002/jctb.4366.

470 Egorova, K.S., Ananikov, V.P., 2014. Toxicity of ionic liquids: Eco(cyto)activity as
471 complicated, but unavoidable parameter for task-specific optimization.
472 *ChemSusChem.* 7, 336–360. doi:10.1002/cssc.201300459.

473 Fabiańska, A., Ossowski, T., Stepnowski, P., Stolte, S., Thöming, J., Siedlecka, E.M.,
474 2012. Electrochemical oxidation of imidazolium-based ionic liquids: The
475 influence of anions. *Chem. Eng. J.* 198–199, 338–345.
476 doi:10.1016/j.cej.2012.05.108.

477 Ford, L., Harjani, J.R., Atefi, F., Garcia, M.T., Singer, R.D., Scammells, P.J., 2010.
478 Further studies on the biodegradation of ionic liquids. *Green Chem.* 12, 1783–
479 1789. doi:10.1039/c0gc00082e.

480 Frade, R.F.M., Afonso, C.A.M., 2010. Impact of ionic liquids in environment and
481 humans: An overview. *Hum. Exp. Toxicol.* 29, 1038–1054.
482 doi:10.1177/0960327110371259.

483 Freire, M.G., Neves, C.M.S.S., Marrucho, I.M., Coutinho, J.A.P., Fernandes, A.M.,
484 2010. Hydrolysis of tetrafluoroborate and hexafluorophosphate counter ions in
485 imidazolium-based ionic liquids. *J. Phys. Chem. A.* 114, 3744–3749.
486 doi:10.1021/jp903292n.

487 Gadilohar, B.L., Kumbhar, H.S., Shankarling, G.S., 2014. Choline Peroxydisulfate:
488 Environmentally friendly biodegradable oxidizing TSIL for selective and rapid
489 oxidation of alcohols. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 53, 19010–19018.
490 doi:10.1021/ie5032919.

491 Gadilohar, B.L., Shankarling, G.S., 2018. Choline based ionic liquids and their
492 applications in organic transformation. *J. Mol. Liq.* 227, 234–261.
493 doi:10.1016/j.molliq.2016.11.136.

494 Garcia, M.T., Gathergood, N., Scammells, P.J., 2005. Biodegradable ionic liquids - Part
495 II. Effect of the anion and toxicology. *Green Chem.* 7, 9–14.
496 doi:10.1039/B411922c.

497 Gathergood, N., Scammells, P.J., Garcia, M.T., 2006. Biodegradable ionic liquids - Part
498 III. The first readily biodegradable ionic liquids. *Green Chem.* 8, 156–160.
499 doi:10.1039/B516206H.

500 Gomez-Herrero, E., Tobajas, M., Polo, A., Rodriguez, J.J., Mohedano, A.F., 2018.
501 Removal of imidazolium- and pyridinium-based ionic liquids by Fenton
502 oxidation. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 25, 34930–34937. doi:10.1007/s11356-017-
503 0867-4.

504 González, E.J., Palomar, J., Navarro, P., Larriba, M., García, J., Rodríguez, F., 2018. On
505 the volatility of aromatic hydrocarbons in ionic liquids: Vapor-liquid equilibrium
506 measurements and theoretical analysis. *J. Mol. Liq.* 250, 9–18.

507 doi:10.1016/j.molliq.2017.11.134.

508 Jing, B., Lan, N., Qiu, J., Zhu, Y., 2016. Interaction of ionic liquids with a lipid bilayer:
509 a biophysical study of ionic liquid cytotoxicity. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 120, 2781–2789.
510 doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b00362.

511 Jordan, A., Gathergood, N., 2015. Biodegradation of ionic liquids - a critical review.
512 *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 44, 8200–8237. doi:10.1039/c5cs00444f.

513 Karadas, F., Köz, B., Jacquemin, J., Deniz, E., Rooney, D., Thompson, J., Yavuz, C.T.,
514 Khraisheh, M., Aparicio, S., Atihan, M., 2013. High pressure CO₂ absorption
515 studies on imidazolium-based ionic liquids: Experimental and simulation
516 approaches. *Fluid Phase Equilib.* 351, 74–86. doi:10.1016/j.fluid.2012.10.022.

517 Kathiresan, M., Velayutham, D., 2015. Ionic liquids as an electrolyte for the electro
518 synthesis of organic compounds. *Chem. Commun.* 51, 17499–17516.
519 doi:10.1039/C5CC06961K.

520 Khan, M.I., Zaini, D., Shariff, A.M., 2016. Framework for ecotoxicological risk
521 assessment of ionic liquids. *Procedia Eng.* 148, 1141–1148.
522 doi:10.1016/j.proeng.2016.06.567.

523 Lemus, J., Palomar, J., Heras, F., Gilarranz, M.A., Rodriguez, J.J., 2012. Developing
524 criteria for the recovery of ionic liquids from aqueous phase by adsorption with
525 activated carbon. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 97, 11–19.
526 doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2012.02.027.

527 Leonardo da Silva, W., Caroline Leal, B., Luiza Ziulkoski, A., van Leeuwen, P. W. N.
528 M., Henrique Zimnoch dos Santos, J., Stephan Schrekker, H., 2019.
529 Petrochemical residue-derived silica-supported titania-magnesium catalysts for
530 the photocatalytic degradation of imidazolium ionic liquids in water. *Sep. Purif.*
531 *Technol.* 218, 191–199. doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2019.01.066.

532 Li, W., Zhang, Z., Han, B., Hu, S., Xie, Y., Yang, G., 2007. Effect of water and organic
533 solvents on-the ionic dissociation of ionic liquids. *J. Phys. Chem. B.* 111, 6452–
534 6456. doi:10.1021/jp071051m.

535 Liu, H., Zhang, X., Chen, C., Du, S., Dong, Y., 2015. Effects of imidazolium chloride

536 ionic liquids and their toxicity to *Scenedesmus obliquus*. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.*
537 122, 83–90. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2015.07.010.

538 Matzke, M., Stolte, S., Thiele, K., Juffernholz, T., Arning, J., Ranke, J., Welz-Birmann,
539 U., Jastorff, B., 2007. The influence of anion species on the toxicity of 1-alkyl-3-
540 methylimidazolium ionic liquids observed in an (eco)toxicological test battery.
541 *Green Chem.* 9, 1198–1207. doi:10.1039/B705795D.

542 Mena, I.F., Cotillas, S., Díaz, E., Sáez, C., Mohedano, A.F., Rodrigo, M.A., 2019a.
543 Sono- and photoelectrocatalytic processes for the removal of ionic liquids based
544 on the 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium cation. *J. Hazard. Mat.* 372, 77–84.
545 doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2017.12.015.

546 Mena, I.F., Díaz, E., Pérez-Farías, C., Stolte, S., Moreno-Andrade, I., Rodriguez, J.J.,
547 Mohedano, A.F., 2019b. Catalytic wet peroxide oxidation of imidazolium-based
548 ionic liquids: Catalyst stability and biodegradability enhancement. *Chem. Eng. J.*
549 (In press). doi:10.1016/j.cej.2018.11.129.

550 Mena, I.F., Díaz, E., Rodriguez, J.J., Mohedano, A.F., 2019c. Biological oxidation of
551 choline-based ionic liquids in sequencing batch reactors. *J. Chem. Technol.*
552 *Biotechnol.* (In press). doi:10.1002/jctb.5954.

553 Montalbán, M.G., Hidalgo, J.M., Collado-González, M., Díaz Baños, F.G., Villora, G.,
554 2016. Assessing chemical toxicity of ionic liquids on *Vibrio fischeri*: Correlation
555 with structure and composition. *Chemosphere.* 155, 405–414.
556 doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.04.042.

557 Montalbán, M.G., Villora, G., Licence, P., 2018. Ecotoxicity assessment of dicationic
558 versus monocationic ionic liquids as a more environmentally friendly alternative.
559 *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 150, 129–135. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2017.11.073.

560 Moya, C., Alonso-Morales, N., Gilarranz, M.A., Rodriguez, J.J., Palomar, J., 2016.
561 Encapsulated Ionic Liquids for CO₂ Capture: Using 1-Butyl-methylimidazolium
562 Acetate for Quick and Reversible CO₂ Chemical Absorption. *ChemPhysChem* 17,
563 3891–3899. doi:10.1002/cphc.201600977.

564 Munoz, M., Domínguez, C.M., De Pedro, Z.M., Quintanilla, A., Casas, J.A., Ventura,
565 S.P.M., Coutinho, J.A.P., 2015. Role of the chemical structure of ionic liquids in

566 their ecotoxicity and reactivity towards Fenton oxidation, Sep. Purif. Technol.
567 150, 252–256. doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2015.07.014.

568 Munoz, M., Domínguez, C.M., De Pedro, Z.M., Quintanilla, A., Casas, J.A., Rodriguez,
569 J.J., 2016. Degradation of imidazolium-based ionic liquids by catalytic wet
570 peroxide oxidation with carbon and magnetic iron catalysts. J. Chem. Technol.
571 Biotechnol. 91, 2882–2887. doi:10.1002/jctb.4904.

572 Nandwani, S.K., Malek, N.I., Lad, V.N., Chakraborty, M., Gupta, S., 2017. Study on
573 interfacial properties of Imidazolium ionic liquids as surfactant and their
574 application in enhanced oil recovery. Colloids Surfaces A Physicochem. Eng.
575 Asp. 516, 383–393. doi:10.1016/j.colsurfa.2016.12.037.

576 Neumann, J., Pawlik, M., Bryniok, D., Thöming, J., Stolte, S., 2014a. Biodegradation
577 potential of cyano-based ionic liquid anions in a culture of *Cupriavidus spp.* and
578 their in vitro enzymatic hydrolysis by nitrile hydratase. Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.
579 21, 9495–9505. doi:10.1007/s11356-013-2341-2.

580 Neumann, J., Steudte, S., Cho, C.-W., Thöming, J., Stolte, S., 2014b. Biodegradability
581 of 27 pyrrolidinium, morpholinium, piperidinium, imidazolium and pyridinium
582 ionic liquid cations under aerobic conditions. Green Chem. 16, 2174–2184.
583 doi:10.1039/C3GC41997E.

584 Neves, C.M.S.S., Lemus, J., Freire, M.G., Palomar, J., Coutinho, J.A.P., 2014.
585 Enhancing the adsorption of ionic liquids onto activated carbon by the addition of
586 inorganic salts. Chem. Eng. J. 252, 305–310. doi:10.1016/j.cej.2014.05.009.

587 Olivier-Bourbigou, H., Magna, L., Morvan, D., 2010. Ionic liquids and catalysis: Recent
588 progress from knowledge to applications. Appl. Catal. A Gen. 373, 1–56.
589 doi:10.1016/j.apcata.2009.10.008.

590 Oulego, P., Blanco, D., Ramos, D., Viesca, J.L., Díaz, M., Hernández Battez, A., 2018.
591 Environmental properties of phosphonium, imidazolium and ammonium cation-
592 based ionic liquids as potential lubricant additives, J. Mol. Liq. 272, 937–947.
593 doi:10.1016/j.molliq.2018.10.106.

594 Pagga, U., 1997. Testing biodegradability with standardized methods, Chemosphere 35,
595 2953–2972.

- 596 Palomar, J., Ferro, V.R., Gilarranz, M.A., Rodriguez, J.J., 2007. Computational
597 approach to nuclear magnetic resonance in 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium ionic
598 liquids, *J. Phys. Chem. B.* 111, 168–180. doi:10.1021/jp063527s.
- 599 Palomar, J., Gonzalez-Miquel, M., Bedia, J., Rodriguez, F., Rodriguez, J.J., 2011. Task-
600 specific ionic liquids for efficient ammonia absorption, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 82,
601 43–52. doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2011.08.014.
- 602 Pandey, S., Baker, G.A., Sze, L., Pandey, S., Kamath, G., Zhao, H., Baker, S.N., 2013.
603 Ionic liquids containing fluorinated β -diketonate anions: synthesis,
604 characterization and potential applications, *New J. Chem.* 37, 909–919.
605 doi:10.1039/c3nj40855h.
- 606 Pârvulescu, V.I., Hardacre, C., 2007. Catalysis in ionic liquids. *Chem. Rev.* 107, 2615–
607 2665. doi:10.1021/cr050948h.
- 608 Peric, B., Sierra, J., Martí, E., Cruañas, R., Garau, M.A., Arning, J., Bottin-Weber, U.,
609 Stolte, S., 2013. (Eco)toxicity and biodegradability of selected protic and aprotic
610 ionic liquids, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 261, 99–105. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2013.06.070.
- 611 Petkovic, M., Seddon, K.R., Rebelo, L.P.N., Pereira, C.S., 2011. Ionic liquids: a
612 pathway to environmental acceptability, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 40, 1383–1403.
613 doi:10.1039/c004968a.
- 614 Pieczyńska, A., Ofiarska, A., Borzyszkowska, A.F., Białk-Bielińska, A., Stepnowski,
615 P., Stolte, S., Siedlecka, E.M., 2015. A comparative study of electrochemical
616 degradation of imidazolium and pyridinium ionic liquids: A reaction pathway and
617 ecotoxicity evaluation. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 156, 522–534.
618 doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2015.10.045.
- 619 Plechkova, N.V., Seddon, K.R., 2008. Applications of ionic liquids in the chemical
620 industry, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 37, 123–150. doi:10.1039/b006677j.
- 621 Polo, A.M., Tobajas, M., Sanchis, S., Mohedano, A.F., Rodriguez, J.J., 2011.
622 Comparison of experimental methods for determination of toxicity and
623 biodegradability of xenobiotic compounds, *Biodegradation.* 22, 751–761.
624 doi:10.1007/s10532-010-9448-7.

- 625 Poza–Nogueiras, V., Arellano, M., Rosales, E., Pazos, M., González–Romero, E.,
626 Sanromán, M.A., 2018. Heterogeneous electro-Fenton as plausible technology for
627 the degradation of imidazolium–based ionic liquids. *Chemosphere* 199, 68–75.
628 doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.01.174.
- 629 Pretti, C., Renzi, M., Focardi, S.E., Giovani, A., Monni, G., Melai, B., Rajamani, S.,
630 Chiappe, C., 2011. Acute toxicity and biodegradability of N-alkyl-N-
631 methylmorpholinium and N-alkyl-DABCO based ionic liquids, *Ecotoxicol.*
632 *Environ. Saf.* 74, 748–753. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2010.10.032.
- 633 Quijano, G., Couvert, A., Amrane, A., Darracq, G., Couriol, C., Le Cloirec, P., Paquin,
634 L., Carrié, D., 2011. Toxicity and biodegradability of ionic liquids: New
635 perspectives towards whole-cell biotechnological applications, *Chem. Eng. J.* 174,
636 27–32. doi:10.1016/j.cej.2011.07.055.
- 637 Radošević, K., Cvjetko Bubalo, M., Gaurina Srček, V., Grgas, D., Landeka Dragičević,
638 T., Redovniković, R.I., 2015. Evaluation of toxicity and biodegradability of
639 choline chloride based deep eutectic solvents, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 112, 46–
640 53. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2014.09.034.
- 641 Ranke, J., Müller, A., Bottin-Weber, U., Stock, F., Stolte, S., Arning, J., Störmann, R.,
642 Jastorff, B., 2007. Lipophilicity parameters for ionic liquid cations and their
643 correlation to in vitro cytotoxicity, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 67, 430–438.
644 doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2006.08.008.
- 645 Richardson, S.D., Kimura, S.Y., 2016. Water analysis: Emerging contaminants and
646 current issues, *Anal. Chem.* 88, 546–582.
647 <http://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.analchem.5b04493>.
- 648 Richardson, S.D., Ternes, T.A., 2014. Water analysis: Emerging contaminants and
649 current issues, *Anal. Chem.* 86, 2813–2848. doi:10.1021/ac500508t.
- 650 Rizzo, L., 2011. Bioassays as a tool for evaluating advanced oxidation processes in
651 water and wastewater treatment, *Water Res.* 45, 4311–4340.
652 doi:10.1016/j.watres.2011.05.035.
- 653 Romero, A., Santos, A., Tojo, J., Rodriguez, A., 2008. Toxicity and biodegradability of
654 imidazolium ionic liquids, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 151, 268–273.

655 doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.10.079.

656 Samori, C., Malferrari, D., Valbonesi, P., Montecavalli, A., Moretti, F., Galletti, P.,
657 Sartor, G., Tagliavini, E., Fabbri, E., Pasteris, A., 2010. Introduction of
658 oxygenated side chain into imidazolium ionic liquids: Evaluation of the effects at
659 different biological organization levels, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 73, 1456–1464.
660 doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2010.07.020.

661 Sanchis, S., Polo, A.M., Tobajas, M., Rodriguez, J.J., Mohedano, A.F., 2014. Strategies
662 to evaluate biodegradability: Application to chlorinated herbicides, *Environ. Sci.*
663 *Pollut. Res.* 21, 9445–9452. doi:10.1007/s11356-013-2130-y.

664 Santos, A.G., Ribeiro, B.D., Alviano, D.S., Coelho, M.A.Z., 2014. Toxicity of ionic
665 liquids toward microorganisms interesting to the food industry, *RSC Adv.* 4,
666 37157–37163. doi:10.1039/C4RA05295A.

667 Sekar, S., Surianarayanan, M., Ranganathan, V., Macfarlane, D.R., Mandal, A.B., 2012.
668 Choline-Based Ionic Liquids-Enhanced Biodegradation of Azo Dyes, *Environ.*
669 *Sci. Technol.* 46, 4902–4908.

670 Sintra, T.E., Nasirpour, M., Siopa, F., Rosatella, A.A., Gonçalves, F., Coutinho, J.A.P.,
671 Afonso, C.A.M., Ventura, S.P.M., 2017. Ecotoxicological evaluation of magnetic
672 ionic liquids, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 143, 315–321.
673 doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2017.05.034.

674 Stassen, H.K., Ludwig, R., Wulf, A., Dupont, J., 2015. Imidazolium salt ion Pairs in
675 solution, *Chem. - A Eur. J.* 21, 8324–8335. doi:10.1002/chem.201500239.

676 Stepnowski, P., Zaleska, A., 2005. Comparison of different advanced oxidation
677 processes for the degradation of room temperature ionic liquids. *J. Photochem.*
678 *Photobiol. A Chem.* 170, 45–50. doi:10.1016/j.jphotochem.2004.07.019.

679 Stolte, S., Abdulkarim, S., Arning, J., Blomeyer-Nienstedt, A.K., Bottin-Weber, U.,
680 Matzke, M., Ranke J., Jastorff, B., Thöming, J., 2008. Primary biodegradation of
681 ionic liquid cations, identification of degradation products of 1-methyl-3-
682 octylimidazolium chloride and electrochemical wastewater treatment of poorly
683 biodegradable compounds, *Green Chem.* 10, 214–224. doi:10.1039/b713095c.

684 Stolte, S., Arning, J., Bottin-Weber, U., Müller, A., Pitner, W.-R., Welz-Biermann, U.,
685 Jastorff, B., Ranke, J., 2007. Effects of different head groups and functionalised
686 side chains on the cytotoxicity of ionic liquids, *Green Chem.* 9, 1170–1179.
687 doi:10.1039/B615326G.

688 Stolte, S., Steudte, S., Areitioaurtena, O., Pagano, F., Thöming, J., Stepnowski, P.,
689 Igartua A., 2012. Ionic liquids as lubricants or lubrication additives: An
690 ecotoxicity and biodegradability assessment, *Chemosphere.* 89, 1135–1141.
691 doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2012.05.102.

692 Thuy Pham, T.P., Cho, C.W., Yun, Y.S., 2010. Environmental fate and toxicity of ionic
693 liquids: A review, *Water Res.* 44, 352–372. doi:10.1016/j.watres.2009.09.030.

694 Torrecilla, J.S., Palomar, J., Lemus, J., Rodríguez, F. A., 2010. Quantum-chemical-
695 based guide to analyze/quantify the cytotoxicity of ionic liquids, *Green Chem.* 12,
696 123–134. doi:10.1039/b919806g.

697 Tsarpali, V., Dailianis, S., 2015. Toxicity of two imidazolium ionic liquids,
698 [bmim][BF₄] and [omim][BF₄], to standard aquatic test organisms: Role of
699 acetone in the induced toxicity, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 117, 62–71.
700 doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2015.03.026.

701 Ventura, S.P.M., e Silva, F.A., Gonçalves, A.M.M., Pereira, J.L., Gonçalves, F.,
702 Coutinho, J.A.P., 2014. Ecotoxicity analysis of cholinium-based ionic liquids to
703 *Vibrio fischeri* marine bacteria, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 102, 48–54.
704 doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2014.01.003.

705 Viboud, S., Papaiconomou, N., Cortesi, A., Chatel, G., Draye, M., Fontvieille, D., 2012.
706 Correlating the structure and composition of ionic liquids with their toxicity on
707 *Vibrio fischeri*: A systematic study, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 215-216, 40–48.
708 doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2012.02.019.

709 Vieira, N.S.M., Stolte, S., Araújo, J.M.M., Rebelo, L.P.N., Pereiro, A.B., Markiewicz,
710 M., 2019. Acute Aquatic Toxicity and Biodegradability of Fluorinated Ionic
711 Liquids, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 7, 3733–3741.
712 doi:10.1021/acssuschemeng.8b03653.

713 Yoo, B., Shah, J.K., Zhu, Y., Maginn, E.J., 2014. Amphiphilic interactions of ionic

- 714 liquids with lipid biomembranes: a molecular simulation study. *Soft Matter* 10,
715 8641–8651. doi:10.1039/C4SM01528B
- 716 Zhang, Q., De Oliveira Vigier, K., Royer, S., Jérôme, F., 2012. Deep eutectic solvents:
717 syntheses, properties and applications, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 41, 7108.
718 doi:10.1039/c2cs35178a.
- 719 Zhao, D., Wu, M., Kou, Y., Min, E., 2002. Ionic liquids: applications in catalysis, *Catal.*
720 *Today* 74, 157–189. doi:10.1016/S0920-5861(01)00541-7.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: